

YouCount
Youth Citizen Science

D5.2

Project Leaflet

Usue Lorenz¹, Nagore Valle¹, Iratxe García¹, Patricia Canto Farachala¹, Susana Franco¹

- ¹ Foundation Deusto/Orkestra, University of Deusto, Donostia-San Sebastian, Spain

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101005931

Project Acronym	YouCount
Project Name	YouCount – Empowering youth and cocreating social innovations and policymaking through youth-focused citizen social science
Grant Agreement no.	101005931
Start date of the project	01 / 02 / 2021
End date of the project	30 /01 /2024
Work Package producing the document	WP-5, Dissemination, exploitation and communication
WP Leader	5, FD
Other Partners involved	1, OsloMet
Deliverable identifier	5.6
Deliverable lead beneficiary	5, FD
Internal Scientific Reviewer	UNIVIE, Joerg Matthes
Due date	31, July, 2021
Date of delivery	Date of submission (to be filled by Coordination Office)
Version	Last version as approved by WP-Leader
Author(s)	5, FD, 1,
Classification	Public

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D5.2 Project Leaflet

The project leaflet is one of the main communication activities within WP5, Dissemination, exploitation and communication which seeks to design and implement an effective and targeted communication and dissemination strategy as expressed in the Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication (DEC) Plan. This deliverable is in line with the aims of WP5 and the DEC Plan, addressing the need of designing and delivering a project leaflet to inform and promote the project activities to multiple audiences and stakeholders and looking to engage with them.

Table 1: Revision history

VERSION	DATE	CREATED BY	COMMENTS
1.0	19 / 07 / 2021	5, FD, Usue Lorenz	First draft with structure and content.
2.0	23 / 07/ 2021	6, UNIVIE, Jörg Matthes	Reviewed draft with comments
3.0	26 / 07 / 2021	5, FD, Usue Lorenz	Final version submitted

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Cited as: Lorenz, U., Valle, N., Garcia, I., Canto-Farachala P. and Franco, S. *YouCount. D5.2 Project Leaflet*. Zenodo. doi. 10.5281/zenodo.5136912

Table 2: Terms and Abbreviations

ABBREVIATION	FULL TERM
AB	Advisory Board
DEC	Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication
DoA	Document of Action
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
GA	General Assembly
SwafS	Science with and for Society
WP	Work Package
YCS	Young Citizen Scientist

Executive Summary

The project leaflet is one of the main communication activities within WP5, Dissemination, exploitation and communication which seeks to design and implement an effective and targeted communication and dissemination strategy as expressed in the Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication (DEC) Plan¹. This deliverable is in line with the aims of WP5 and the DEC Plan, addressing the need of designing and delivering a project leaflet to inform and promote the project activities to multiple audiences and stakeholders and looking to engage with them.

This deliverable describes the project leaflet development process in two different key moments of the project implementation where there is a need to inform about it: at the beginning of the project (2021 leaflet -M6) and at the end of the project (2023 leaflet - M34). It also describes the principles that drive the design of both leaflets in terms of objectives sought, main target public, the use of language and the end format (paper / digital). It also contains the set of leaflets designed for 2021: the general leaflet that contains the information of all case studies and the customised leaflet by country that only contains the information about the specific case and that is designed to facilitate translation into the local languages by each partner.

¹ Canto-Farachala P., Lorenz, U., Franco, S., Brounéus, F., Norvoll, R. and Hummer, P. *YouCount. D.5.7 Continuous, updated DEC and stakeholder engagement plan, and report on DEC activities*. Zenodo. doi.10.5281/zenodo.4812107

1 Introduction

According to the DoA, “a leaflet outlining the project will be developed to be distributed by project partners in their countries and to their stakeholder groups and networks in the relevant languages. In month 34, a second leaflet will be produced, highlighting the main results of the project”.

The project leaflet is a deliverable of WP5, Dissemination, exploitation and communication, which seeks to design and implement an effective and targeted communication and dissemination strategy with the main stakeholder groups of YouCount as defined in section 4 of the DEC Plan².

The DEC Plan is the main deliverable of WP5 which sets the means by which to maximise the project’s overall impact by means of:

- Designing and implementing effective and targeted dissemination strategies to enable the uptake of project outputs.
- Designing and implementing an effective and targeted communication strategy with multilevel stakeholder engagement (including the academic community) to support the mobilisation of a wide variety of actors.
- Designing and implementing an exploitation strategy to ensure the best possible use of YouCount results after the end of the EU-funded project.

In line with this plan, communication activities aim to inform and promote the project activities on a continuous basis to multiple audiences, looking specifically to engage with the project multilevel platform and to carry out targeted communication with the stakeholders to mobilise and retain their involvement in CS in the social sciences. This deliverable corresponds to the communication activity of delivering a project leaflet. According to the DEC Plan, it is foreseen the delivery of two leaflets: one in month 6 and the other one in month 34. The first one would present the project objectives and the second one would present the project results.

The leaflets’ design meets with the requirements of D5.1 Project identity and website, especially with the Project Identity Guidelines¹ and in accordance with the elements that make up the YouCount identity system. It also meets with the requirements of the section 5 (Communication Structures and Procedures) of the D6.1 Project Executive Handbook that sets out the external communication and dissemination.

² Canto-Farachala P., Lorenz, U., Franco, S., Brounéus, F., Norvoll, R. and Hummer, P. *YouCount. D.5.7 Continuous, updated DEC and stakeholder engagement plan, and report on DEC activities*. Zenodo. doi.10.5281/zenodo.4812107

2 Project Leaflet Objectives

Following the DEC Plan, the project leaflet is the communication activity that seeks to give more information about the project to the main stakeholder groups of YouCount, particularly among stakeholders who are not active in social media or directly involved in the project. The partners will distribute printed copies of the leaflets in their own countries to increase the project’s visibility. This way they have something tangible that leads them to more information about the project.

The following table summarizes the main features of the two leaflets to be delivered in the project lifetime. These features have been agreed between the project partners, following the DEC Plan and the project requirements in terms of the dissemination’s activities contained in the project Handbook and the Project identity Guidelines.

The DEC Plan states that ‘the youth and the researchers will participate in the design of the different tools to carry out the project communication activities from the early stages’. Youth have not been involved at this stage of the project implementation as the consortium is at the beginning of the research process and the case studies’ development and youth engagement is at their very first steps. The project leaflet design focus has been agreed only among project members, while youth involvement will be incorporated in later stages for the development phase of the second leaflet design in M34.

Table 3. Main features of the project leaflet

	Version 1 (M6 – July 2021)	Version 2 (M34 – Dic 2023)
Languages	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> English Local language 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> English Local language
Target group	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Local youth Policymakers and community stakeholders, employers and end user organisations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Academic community CS projects in the call (SwafS) University institutions
Focus	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> General overview of the objective and the cases 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> First results of YouCount and case studies
Printing / Digital	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Number of copies – distributed: 900 (100 each case) Online leaflet 	

Some principles that have been adopted throughout the leaflet design process are the following ones:

- **Focus:**
 - The 2021 leaflet will seek to introduce the social inclusion challenge of youngsters in Europe, call youth to take action as citizen scientists, a brief explanation of what does it mean in general terms, and a brief explanation of our hands-on citizen science projects or case studies.
 - The 2023 leaflet will seek to inform about the first results of YouCount and the case studies and it will target stakeholders/academia.
- **Target group:** the 2021 leaflet will target local youth and stakeholders, while the 2023 leaflet will be addressing the academic community and stakeholders.
- **Types of leaflet (2021):**
 - General leaflet: it will contain all the cases description
 - Customised leaflet per each of the national case: it contains only its case description.
- **Language (leaflet 2021):**
 - The leaflets are produced in English
 - Leaflet design allows translation into local language and all partners can edit it. The English version will be provided for each partner. Each customized leaflet will be provided in PowerPoint version, allowing edition and translation into local languages. An instruction manual will be provided to each partner (see Appendix D).
 - Positive language and plain language have been the main principles followed for writing the text.
- **Digital / paper format:**
 - Each partner is committed to print 100 copies of the paper format of the leaflet, adding the paper copies of the leaflet 2021 and 2023, for its local distribution.
 - The leaflets will have a digital format for its distribution through digital means (readable by phone and computers).

3. Project leaflet design – M6

The 2021 leaflets, both the general and customized ones, are formed by three different sections as it is shown in Appendix A:

1. **Section 1:** general introduction to the challenge of youth in Europe and the general aim of the project.

The Consortium has provided three different text options for section 1 as it is shown in Appendix A. Option A is the simplest one in terms of not incorporating any concept such as social inclusion; option B includes more concepts than A, such as Social Inclusion; and, option C is similar to B, but with a slightly different definitions of Y-CSS.

2. **Section 2.** It is a plain explanation of the concepts of social inclusion and what does it mean for Y-CSS to become one of them.
3. **Section 3.** It contains a map showing all the case study locations. The general leaflet will introduce all the case studies, while the customized leaflets by case study will introduce only the local case study.

Other characteristic of the leaflets is the possibility given to each country case study to customize the leaflet. Each research team has been able to decide the preferred option of section 1, which has resulted in 9 different customised leaflets. For the general leaflet, option B has been the text agreed among project members. The following table summarizes the combination of texts agreed for each customized leaflet in the local locations.

Table 4. Combination of texts for the customized leaflet, by case study

Nº Leaflet	Case study		Description	Option
1	1	Norway	Young Citizen Social Scientists in Gamle Oslo District, Oslo (Norway) will explore "What are the drivers for social inclusion through youth employability and social entrepreneurship in the city?"	A or B
2	2	Sweden	Young Citizen Social Scientists in Sweden will explore: In what ways do engagement in the Botkyrka Youth Council lead to other forms of social inclusion, and how can we help more young people to engage in civil society activities? Short version: Can engagement in a youth city council lead to other forms of social inclusion?"	A
3	3	UK	In Preston young citizen scientists or researchers will explore – What influences whether or not young people feel they belong?	A
4	4	Spain	Young Citizen Scientist in the Basque Country (Spain) will explore Which are the inclusion factors for young migrants in our society?	B
5	5	Austria	Young Citizen Scientist in Austria will explore: Which civic engagement opportunities do young migrants have and which opportunities are missing for young migrants to meaningfully participate?	B
6	6	Lithuania	Young Citizen Social Scientists in Panevezys district (Lithuania) will explore What influences whether or not young people feel they belong to community?	C
7	7	Denmark	Young people in the South Harbour neighbourhood in Copenhagen (Denmark) will explore: How they can engage in local repairing and sharing activities in order to reduce their resource consumption and climate impact	
8	8	Hungary 1	Hard of hearing youth in Szeged (Hungary) will explore What challenges do they perceive and what resources are available for them in the process of becoming autonomous and independent adults? Short version: What are the challenges and enablers in becoming autonomous adults?	A
	9	Hungary 2	The Citizen Social Scientists from Siklósbodony (Hungary) will explore the social constraints and local possibilities around adopting sustainable agriculture techniques and gaining better access to quality education	
9	10	Italy	In Naples, Italy, Young Citizen Scientists will explore	C

			Which are the drivers for social inclusion of young migrants in the hosting local community?	
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The general leaflet indigital and print format is shown in Appendix B and the customised leaflets by country in the English version are shown in Appendix C.

Appendixes

Table 5: Appendixes

APPENDIX	SUBJECT	PAGE
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Appendix D	How to edit the leaflet	18

Appendix A. Project Leaflet 2021 (M6)

SECTION 1:

Option A

‘YouCount’ – A research project about the lives of European youth. Be part of YouCount and help improve young people’s futures!

Young people know more about their own lives, hopes and dreams than anyone else.

So, a team of researchers from nine European countries will work with young ‘citizen scientists’ to find new solutions to local challenges producing positive change for youth in your community.

Join the YouCount community!

Your thoughts count!

Option B

‘YouCount’ – A research project about the lives of European youth. Be part of YouCount and help improve young people’s futures!

Young people in Europe are facing many challenges related to social inclusion. Young people know more about their own lives, hopes and dreams than anyone else. They can contribute with important knowledge about

- The critical issues regarding social inclusion
- The opportunities for social inclusion of young people and the positive drivers for change

So, in this project **young people can be involved as young ‘citizen scientists’ and work together** with a team of researchers from nine European countries in finding new solutions to local challenges producing positive change for youth in your community.

Please join! Your thoughts count.

Option C:

Youths in Europe are facing many challenges related to social inclusion

YouCount aims at contributing to successful strategies for social inclusion that require better knowledge on

- What young people, such as YOU, see as crucial issues for increasing social inclusion
- YOUR experiences of opportunities for social inclusion in your daily life

Young people can be involved as young ‘citizen scientists’ helping to produce positive change as ‘lived experts’ and ‘change-makers’ in innovation and policymaking.

Please join! Your thoughts count.

SECTION 2:

Social Inclusion could be....

- Taking part in society, such as having a job or participating in social life
- Feeling connected to others, and a sense of belonging
- Being a ‘citizen’ with rights and responsibilities

Being a young citizen scientist or researcher in YouCount means:

- Exploring what social inclusion means to you and other young people
- Meeting and talking with young people and others

- Identifying possibilities for change based on young people’s ideas
- Working together with community leaders to create change

SECTION 3: 2nd page starts here with Europe Map – highlighting the case study locations

Each partner’s leaflet will include their case study description (only theirs). Find below the descriptions available so far:

Nº Leaflet	Case study		Description	Option
1	1	Norway	Young Citizen Social Scientists in Gamle Oslo District, Oslo (Norway) will explore “What are the drivers for social inclusion through youth employability and social entrepreneurship in the city?”	A or B
2	2	Sweden	Young Citizen Social Scientists in Sweden will explore: In what ways do engagement in the Botkyrka Youth Council lead to other forms of social inclusion, and how can we help more young people to engage in civil society activities? Short version: Can engagement in a youth city council lead to other forms of social inclusion?”	A
3	3	UK	In Preston young citizen scientists or researchers will explore – What influences whether or not young people feel they belong?	A
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8	8	Hungary 1	Hard of hearing youth in Szeged (Hungary) will explore What challenges do they perceive and what resources are available for them in the process of becoming autonomous and independent adults? Short version: What are the challenges and enablers in becoming	A

			autonomous adults?	
9		Hungary 2	The Citizen Social Scientists from Siklósbodony (Hungary) will explore the social constraints and local possibilities around adopting sustainable agriculture techniques and gaining better access to quality education	
9	10	Italy	In Naples, Italy, Young Citizen Scientists will explore Which are the drivers for social inclusion of young migrants in the hosting local community?	C

Insert -

	General leaflet	Leaflet per country
Website	www.youcountproject.eu (with a hyperlink)	
Hashtags:	#youcountproject #CitizenSocialScience; #CitSci, #SwafS, #youth; #Social Inclusion	
Social media	Twitter: @youcountproject Facebook: @youcountproject	
Logo	All partners' logos	Logo of the national partner only
	EU logo + "This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101005931"	
Getting in touch:	NA	E-mail (local e-mail to decide locally)
General project information	Starting date: February 2021 Duration: 36 months	

Appendix B. General leaflet –M6, 2021

YouCount

A research project about the lives of European youth

Be part of YouCount and help improve young people's futures!

Young people know more about their own lives, hopes and dreams than anyone else.

So, a team of researchers from nine European countries will work with young **citizen scientists** to find new solutions to local challenges producing positive change for youth in your community.

Join the YouCount community!
Your thoughts count!

Getting in touch

#YouCount

Partners

www.youcountproject.eu

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YouCount
Youth Citizen Science

CITIZEN SCIENCE

YOUTH

EUROPE

CHANGE

Social inclusion could be...

Being a young citizen scientist or researcher in YouCount means:

- 1 Exploring what **social inclusion** means to you and other young people.
- 2 **Meeting and talking** with young people and others.
- 3 Identifying **possibilities for change** based on young people's ideas.
- 4 Working together with community leaders to **create change**.

Young citizen scientists in Europe will explore...

Appendix C. Customized leaflets, M6, 2021

YouCoun

A research project about the lives of European youth

Young people in Europe are facing many challenges related to social inclusion

Young people know more about their own lives, hopes and dreams than anyone else. They can contribute with important knowledge about

- The critical issues regarding social inclusion
- The opportunities for social inclusion of young people and the positive drivers for change

So, in this project **young people can be involved as young 'citizen scientists' and work together** with a team of researchers from nine European countries in finding new solutions to local challenges producing positive change for youth in your community.

Please join!
Your thoughts count

Getting in touch

xxxxxx@xxxxx.com

Partners

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Young Citizen Scientist in **Austria** will explore which civic engagement opportunities do young migrants have and which opportunities are missing for young migrants to meaningfully participate

universität
wien

YouCount

A research project about the lives of European youth

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Your thoughts count!

Getting in touch

msjo@plan.aau.dk

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Young people in the **South Harbour neighbourhood in Copenhagen** will explore how they can engage in local repairing and sharing activities in order to reduce their resource consumption and climate impact

AALBORG UNIVERSITY
DENMARK

YouCount

A research project about the lives of European youth

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Getting in touch

barbaramihok@gmail.com (Szeged)
oblath@gmail.com (Siklósbodony)

#YouCount

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Hard of hearing youth in **Szeged** will explore what challenges do they perceive and what resources are available for them in the process of becoming autonomous and independent adults

The Citizen Social Scientists from **Siklósbodony** will explore the social constraints and local possibilities around adopting sustainable agriculture techniques and gaining better access to quality education

YouCount

Youths in Europe are facing many challenges related to social inclusion

YouCount aims at contributing to successful strategies for social inclusion that require better knowledge on

- What young people, such as YOU, see as crucial issues for increasing social inclusion
- YOUR experiences of opportunities for social inclusion in your daily live

Young people can be involved as young **citizen scientists** helping to produce positive change as 'lived experts' and 'change-makers' in innovation and policymaking.

Please join!
Your thoughts count

Getting in touch

fortuna.procentese@unina.it

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In **Naples** Young Citizen Scientists will explore Which are the drivers for social inclusion of young migrants in the hosting local community?

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egle.butkeviciene@ktu.lt

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Young Citizen Social Scientists in **Panevezys district** will explore what influences whether or not young people feel they belong to community

YouCount

A research project about the lives of European youth

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haai@oslomet.no

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Young Citizen Social Scientists in **Gamle Oslo District** will explore what are the drivers for social inclusion through youth employability and social entrepreneurship in the city

OSLOMET

YouCount

A research project about the lives of European youth

Young people in Europe are facing many challenges related to social inclusion.

Young people know more about their own lives, hopes and dreams than anyone else. They can contribute with important knowledge about:

- The critical issues regarding social inclusion
- The opportunities for social inclusion of young people and the positive drivers for change

So, in this project young people can be involved as young citizen scientists and work together with a team of researchers from nine European countries in finding new solutions to local challenges producing positive change for youth in your community.

Please join!
Your thoughts count

Getting in touch

youcount@orquestra.deusto.es

#YouCount

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Young Citizen Scientist in the **Basque Country** will explore which are the inclusion factors for young migrants in our society

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Getting in touch

fredrik@v-a.se

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Young Citizen Social Scientists in **Sweden** will explore in what ways do engagement in the **Botkyrka Youth Council** lead to other forms of social inclusion, and how can we help more young people to engage in civil society activities

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dcrook5@uclan.ac.uk

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- 4 Working together with community leaders to **create change**.

Young citizen scientists in **Preston** will explore what influences whether or not young people feel they belong to a community

University of
Central Lancashire
UCLan

Appendix D. How to edit the Leaflet

Leaflet editing instructions

1. The first step is to install the font “Ek Mukta” available for download in the link below:

[ek-mukta.zip](#)
2.9 MB

- How to install fonts in Windows: <https://support.microsoft.com/en-us/office/add-a-font-b7c5f17c-4426-4b53-967f-455339c564c1>
- How to install fonts in Mac: <https://support.apple.com/en-us/HT201749>

2. Once the font is installed, **download the Power Point of your country case**. It’s important to open the file in **Power Point** (do not use google slides) so that the elements do not move.

To download:

3. Once downloaded, **make a copy of the PPT file** and name it differently to create a version in your local language.

4. Open the copied file and start editing it. Choose the text box you want to edit by clicking on it, and translate the content. It’s important to try to **use the same typography, font sizes and colors** to keep some consistency among all leaflets.

5. Once the leaflet is completely translated, the last step is to save and export the changes. To do this, at the upper left side, where it says file, you will find an “**Export**” option. There you will be able to export the file in PDF format.

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